

Windows Accounts Security

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Abstract. In different ages, people tried to create risks for their own interests. In this century, Cyber security is the most important thing in life. Governments, fraudsters, etc. create dangerous conditions for people who use the Internet. Now in organizations, some people want to access the accounts of their managers, some want to destroy a website, some want to crack a software to use it freely, and many similar situations we see in hacking. We found many ways to crack windows account password and solutions for them. For example account can be accessible by rainbow table, access administrator shell and brute force. also it have a solution. for example you can encrypt your hard drive to prevent these attacks.

Keywords: Cracking · Hacking · Windows Accounts · Windows Login

1 Introduction

1.1 Hacking

Hacking is the technique of finding the weak links or loopholes in the computer systems or the networks and exploiting it to gain unauthorized access to data or to change the features of the target computer systems or the networks. Hacking describes the modification in the computer hardware, software or the networks to accomplish certain goals which are not aligned with the user goals. In contrast, it is also called breaking into someone's security and stealing their personal or secret data such as phone numbers, credit card details, addresses, online banking passwords etc.[1]

2 Rainbow Table

Rainbow tables are basically huge tables filled with hash values and are used to find required password. Rainbow Table is used by the hackers to find the password by reversing the hashing function. [2]

3 Access Admin Shell

Also you can access windows command prompt in Lock screen without administrator password! that means you can replace command prompt executable file with sticky key executable file(sethc.exe) with live OS or windows installing setup

file browser. (All of them are in System32 Folder) Then press Shift for 5 times in Lock screen to run command prompt run this command and replace "User" with username and "Password" with Your new password: **net user "User" "Password"**

4 Brute Force

In hacking world when we want to find a password, we make many passwords by an algorithm and try them one by one. This is a Brute Force but it isn't fast so you may have to wait a long time. [3]

5 Solution

There is a way to keep your Windows PC safe. if PC hard drive hasn't had encryption they password can be cracked. but that is good idea to have a strong password to keeping it safer than before.

6 Results

Windows is the most useful operating system for PCs. so its security is really important. As you understand you can access users desktop as fast as a lightning so we suggest you to choose a strong password and encrypt your hard.

7 Conclusion

Windows is a good operating system for PCs and organizations computers. But every softwares and operating systems have some issues and Problems. We have many ways to crack windows password and access users desktop and files. for keep your Windows account safe you should have a good password and a encrypted Hard Disk.

References

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